

Cognitive Impairment in Multiple Sclerosis: an IMSCOG Overview of Systematic Reviews Protocol

Authors

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Abstract

Background. Cognitive impairment (CI) is a prevalent and disabling symptom in people with multiple sclerosis (PwMS), affecting various cognitive domains and contributing to reduced quality of life. However, the definitions of CI and the screening tools used in research and clinical settings vary widely.

Aim. This overview of systematic reviews aims to provide a summary of the current definitions of CI and the main cognitive tests used in clinical practice to screen for CI in studies targeting PwMS.

Methods. The review will include systematic reviews focusing on cognitive impairment in PwMS aged 18 and older. The review will be developed and reported according to the JBI methodological guidance for umbrella reviews and to the PRIOR statement, respectively.

Findings. This overview of systematic reviews will summarize the definitions of cognitive impairment and the screening tests employed in clinical practice of published systematic reviews of studies assessing cognitive impairment in PwMS.

Introduction

Cognitive impairment (CI) is a complication of MS that has a significant impact on the day-to-day life of persons living with MS (PwMS). Yet, there are currently no standard criteria for identification and diagnosis of CI in MS. The typical convention in research is to create a dichotomy: identify impaired vs unimpaired individuals. The criteria used to make this distinction vary across studies, but often identify the number of test performances that need to fall below a specified threshold when compared to a group of individuals without MS.

The significant variability in how CI is identified is likely contributing to mixed results observed in intervention trials and may also affect how PwMS experiencing cognitive symptoms are identified and treated in clinical settings.

Objectives

To provide an overview of the definitions of CI and of tests employed to screen for CI in people affected by multiple sclerosis (PwMS) in systematic reviews (SRs). This overview of SRs is part of an International Multiple Sclerosis Cognition Society (IMSCOGS)-European Committee for Treatment and Research in Multiple Sclerosis (ECTRIMS) collaborative project, aimed at reaching a formal consensus on how to define and assess CI in PwMS. The results of this review will be used as an evidence base to inform the consensus process.

Methods

This overview of SRs will be conducted according to the methodology outlined by the JBI for umbrella reviews (Aromataris et al., 2015) and following the preferred reporting items for overviews of reviews (PRIOR) statement recommendations.(Gates et al., 2022)

Eligibility criteria

SRs with a focus on cognitive impairment in people with MS will be the unit of analysis. To be considered as systematic a review should represent syntheses of empirical research evidence, report clear predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria and have searched at least two bibliographic databases. Reviews that incorporate theoretical studies or text and opinion as their primary source of evidence will be excluded.

We will consider for inclusion SRs of randomized controlled trials and non-randomized studies (including controlled and uncontrolled studies and case-series).

Overlapping of primary studies contained within the included SRs will be mapped in order to identify redundancy.

Eligible SRs must include individual studies on adult participants (aged 18 years or older) diagnosed, by means of any diagnostic criteria, with Clinically Isolated Syndrome (CIS),

Relapsing-Remitting Multiple Sclerosis (RRMS), Primary-Progressive MS (PPMS), Secondary Progressive MS (SPMS). Studies including people with Radiologically Isolated Syndrome (RIS) will be considered only if published since 2023.

SRs including mixed populations of adult and paediatric patients or with conditions other than MS will be excluded.

SRs must provide a definition of acquired cognitive impairment, disorder or dysfunction. Definition may also include a threshold for impairment based on a cognitive test score or a battery of tests formally measuring cognitive impairment by means of a neuropsychological tool. SRs including only primary studies adopting self-administered tests or primarily addressing topics other than MS and cognitive impairment will be excluded, as well as narrative reviews, grey literature, reviews reported as conference abstracts, conference proceedings or protocols.

Information sources

Relevant literature will be identified through a comprehensive search of peer-reviewed articles from the following electronic databases: MEDLINE (PubMed), Embase (Ovid), PsychInfo, Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) and the Cochrane Library.

Search strategy

The search strategy for each database will be tailored using a combination of topic-specific keywords, linked through Boolean operators (Appendix 1). An information specialist (CB) will assist in designing and performing the search. Studies published since January 1, 2001 in English language and in peer-reviewed journals will be considered.

Data management

Reference screening will be performed on the online platform Rayyan (Ouzzani, Hammady, Fedorowicz, & Elmagarmid, 2016), and managed accordingly. Quality evaluation of the included systematic reviews will be performed by two reviewers independently using the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for systematic reviews and research syntheses tool. (Aromataris et al., 2015). Two reviewers will independently conduct the screening process, starting with the title and abstract, followed by full-text review. Any disagreements or uncertainties will be resolved by a third author.

One reviewer will extract relevant information into a tailored data extraction spreadsheet, the items of which can be found in Appendix 2. A second reviewer will double-check the extracted information. Discrepancies will be resolved by discussion. The data extraction spreadsheet will be piloted by two reviewers on a set of 10 SRs in order to guarantee data extraction accuracy and consistency.

Data analysis

Data will be presented qualitatively and by means of descriptive statistics in tables and graphs summarizing the findings of the included SRs. The online software EPPI-Mapper (Centre., 2023) will be used to present our results in the form of an evidence table, visually synthesizing

the definitions of cognitive impairment and the screening tools employed in the included studies.

References

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Appendix 1 – Search strategies

Medline (PubMed)

("Cognitive Dysfunction"[Majr] OR Cognit* Dysfunction*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* Disorder*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* Impairment*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* Decline*[Title/Abstract] OR Mental Deterioration*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* function*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* outcome*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* deficit*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* progression*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* status[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* characteristic*[Title/Abstract] OR Cognit* defect*[Title/Abstract]) AND ("Multiple Sclerosis"[Mesh:noexp] OR "clinically isolated syndrome"[Title/Abstract] OR "demyelinating disorder"[Title/Abstract] OR "demyelinating disease"[Title/Abstract] OR "optic neuritis"[Title/Abstract] OR "multiple sclerosis"[Title/Abstract] OR "Demyelinating Autoimmune Diseases, CNS"[Mesh:noexp] OR "Optic Neuritis"[Mesh] OR "Demyelinating Diseases"[Mesh:noexp] OR "Multiple Sclerosis, Relapsing-Remitting"[Mesh] OR "Multiple Sclerosis, Chronic Progressive"[Mesh] OR Radiologically isolated Syndrome[title/abstract] OR RIS[title/abstract])

AND

("Systematic Review"[Publication Type:NoExp] OR "Systematic Reviews as Topic"[mesh:noexp] OR "Cochrane Database Syst Rev"[Journal] OR "Evid Rep Technol Assess (Full Rep)"[jour] OR "Evid Rep Technol Assess (Summ)"[jour] OR "scoping"[TI] OR "systematic"[TI] OR (((("comprehensive analysis" [TIAB:~1] OR "comprehensive review" [TIAB:~1] OR "comprehensively reviewed" [TIAB:~1] OR "literature search" [TIAB:~1] OR "literature searches" [TIAB:~1] OR "scoping search" [TIAB:~1] OR "scoping searches" [TIAB:~1]) NOT "narrative review"[TI]) OR "pooled study" [TIAB:~1] OR "systematic search" [TIAB:~1] OR "systematic searches" [TIAB:~1] OR "systematically searched" [TIAB:~1] AND (databases[TIAB] OR "cinahl" [TIAB] OR "cochrane" [TIAB] OR "embase" [TIAB] OR "psycinfo" [TIAB] OR "pubmed" [TIAB] OR "medline" [TIAB] OR "scopus" [TIAB] OR "web science" [TIAB:~1] OR "bibliographic review" [TIAB:~1] OR "bibliographic reviews" [TIAB:~1] OR "literature review" [TIAB:~1] OR "literature reviews" [TIAB:~1]) OR (("electronic database" [TIAB:~1] OR "electronic databases" [TIAB:~1] OR "databases searched" [TIAB:~3]) AND (eligibility [TIAB] OR excluded [TIAB] OR exclusion [TIAB] OR included [TIAB] OR inclusion [TIAB])) OR ("comparative effectiveness" [TIAB:~1] AND "effectiveness review" [TIAB:~2]) OR ("critical interpretive" [TIAB:~1] AND ("interpretive review" [TIAB:~0] OR "interpretive synthesis" [TIAB:~0])) OR ("diagnostic test" [TIAB:~0] AND ("accuracy review" [TIAB] OR "accuracy reviews" [TIAB] OR "accuracy studies" [TIAB] OR "accuracy study" [TIAB]) AND (meta-analysis [TIAB] OR scoping [TIAB] OR systematic [TIAB])) OR ("evidence assessment" [TIAB] AND GRADE [TIAB]) OR ("evidence gap" [TIAB:~2] AND "gap map" [TIAB:~0]) OR "evidence mapping" [TIAB] OR "evidence review" [TIAB] OR "exploratory review" [TIAB] OR "framework synthesis" [TIAB] OR "mapping review" [TIAB:~1] OR "meta epidemiological" [TIAB] OR "meta ethnographic" [TIAB:~0] OR metaethnographic [TIAB] OR "meta ethnography"

[TIAB:~0] OR metaethnography [TIAB] OR "meta interpretation" [TIAB:~1] OR "meta narrative" [TIAB:~1] OR "meta review" [TIAB:~1] OR "meta study" [TIAB:~1] OR "meta synthesis" [TIAB:~0] OR metasynthesis [TIAB] OR "meta summary" [TIAB:~1] OR "meta theory" [TIAB:~1] OR "methodological review" [TIAB:~1] OR "methodology review" [TIAB:~1] OR ("mixed methods" [TIAB:~0] AND "methods review" [TIAB:~1]) OR ("mixed methods" [TIAB:~0] AND "methods synthesis" [TIAB:~1]) OR "narrative synthesis" [TIAB:~1] OR "overview reviews" [TIAB:~4] OR ("PRISMA" [TIAB] AND (guideline [TIAB] OR guidelines [TIAB] OR preferred [TIAB] OR reporting [TIAB] OR requirements [TIAB])) OR "PRISMA-P" [TIAB:~0] OR "prognostic review" [TIAB:~1] OR "psychometric review" [TIAB:~1] OR ("qualitative evidence" [TIAB:~0] AND "evidence synthesis" [TIAB:~0]) OR ("qualitative research" [TIAB:~0] AND "research synthesis" [TIAB:~0]) OR ("rapid evidence" [TIAB:~0] AND "evidence assessment" [TIAB:~0]) OR "rapid realist" [TIAB:~0] OR "rapid review" [TIAB:~1] OR "rapid reviews" [TIAB:~1] OR "realist review" [TIAB:~1] OR ("review economic" [TIAB:~1] AND ("economic evaluation" [TIAB:~1] OR "economic evaluations" [TIAB:~1])) OR "review reviews" [TIAB:~1] OR "realist syntheses" [TIAB:~1] OR "realist synthesis" [TIAB:~1] OR "scoping review" [TIAB:~2] OR "scoping reviews" [TIAB:~2] OR "scoping studies" [TIAB:~2] OR "scoping study" [TIAB:~2] OR "systematic evidence map" [TIAB] OR "systematic mapping" [TIAB:~2] OR "systematic literature" [TIAB:~1] OR "systematic Medline" [TIAB:~2] OR "systematic PubMed" [TIAB:~2] OR "systematic review" [TIAB:~2] OR "systematic reviews" [TIAB:~2] OR "systematical review" [TIAB:~1] OR "systematical reviews" [TIAB:~2] OR "systematically identified" [TIAB:~1] OR "systematically review" [TIAB:~1] OR "systematically reviewed" [TIAB:~1] OR "systematized review" [TIAB:~1] OR "umbrella review" [TIAB:~2] OR "umbrella reviews" [TIAB:~2])

Filters: English, Humans, from 2001

EMBASE

('multiple sclerosis'/exp OR 'multiple sclerosis':ab,ti OR 'clinically isolated syndrome':ab,ti OR 'demyelinating disorder':ab,ti OR 'optic neuritis'/exp OR 'optic neuritis':ab,ti OR 'demyelinating disease':ab,ti OR 'demyelinating disease'/de OR 'radiologically isolated syndrome':ab,ti OR RIS:ab,ti) AND ('cognitive defect'/mj OR 'cognit* dysfunction*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* disorder*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* impairment*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* decline*':ab,ti OR 'mental deterioration*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* function*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* outcome*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* deficit*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* progression*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* status':ab,ti OR 'cognit* characteristic*':ab,ti OR 'cognit* defect*':ab,ti)

AND

'systematic review'/de OR 'systematic review (topic)/de OR (('comprehensive':ti,ab,kw OR 'mapping':ti,ab,kw OR 'methodology':ti,ab,kw OR 'scoping':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic':ti,ab,kw) AND ('search':ti,ab,kw OR 'searched':ti,ab,kw OR 'searches':ti,ab,kw OR 'studies':ti,ab,kw) AND ('cinahl':ti,ab,kw OR 'cochrane':ti,ab,kw OR 'embase':ti,ab,kw OR 'psycinfo':ti,ab,kw OR

'pubmed':ti,ab,kw OR 'medline':ti,ab,kw OR 'scopus':ti,ab,kw OR 'web of science':ti,ab,kw OR 'bibliographic review':ti,ab,kw OR 'bibliographic reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'literature review':ti,ab,kw OR 'literature reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'literature search':ti,ab,kw OR 'literature searches':ti,ab,kw OR 'qualitative review':ti,ab,kw OR 'qualitative reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'quantitative review':ti,ab,kw OR 'quantitative reviews':ti,ab,kw)) OR 'comprehensive review':ti,ab,kw OR 'comprehensive reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'comprehensive search':ti,ab,kw OR 'comprehensive searches':ti,ab,kw OR 'critical review':ti,ab,kw OR 'critical reviews':ti,ab,kw OR (('electronic database':ti,ab,kw OR 'electronic databases':ti,ab,kw OR databases NEAR/3 searched) AND (eligibility:ti,ab,kw OR excluded:ti,ab,kw OR exclusion:ti,ab,kw OR included:ti,ab,kw OR inclusion:ti,ab,kw)) OR 'evidence assessment':ti,ab,kw OR 'evidence review':ti,ab,kw OR 'exploratory review':ti,ab,kw OR 'framework synthesis':ti,ab,kw OR 'mapping review':ti,ab,kw OR 'meta-review':ti,ab,kw OR 'meta-synthesis':ti,ab,kw OR 'methodology review':ti,ab,kw OR 'mixed methods review':ti,ab,kw OR 'mixed methods synthesis':ti,ab,kw OR (overview NEAR/4 reviews) OR 'PRISMA':ab OR ('preferred':ti,ab,kw and reporting:ti,ab,kw) OR 'prognostic review':ti,ab,kw OR 'psychometric review':ti,ab,kw OR 'rapid evidence assessment':ti,ab,kw OR 'rapid literature review':ti,ab,kw OR 'rapid literature search':ti,ab,kw OR 'rapid realist':ti,ab,kw OR 'rapid review':ti,ab,kw OR 'rapid reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'realist review':ti,ab,kw OR 'review of reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'scoping review':ti,ab,kw OR 'scoping reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'scoping study':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic evidence map':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic evidence mapping':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic literature':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic Medline':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic PubMed':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic review':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic search':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematic searches':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematical literature review':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematical review':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematical reviews':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematically identified':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematically review':ti,ab,kw OR 'systematically reviewed':ti,ab,kw OR 'umbrella review':ti,ab,kw OR 'umbrella reviews':ti,ab,kw OR '13616137':is OR 'Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews'/jt

AND

[english]/lim AND (2001:py OR 2002:py OR 2003:py OR 2004:py OR 2005:py OR 2006:py OR 2007:py OR 2008:py OR 2009:py OR 2010:py OR 2011:py OR 2012:py OR 2013:py OR 2014:py OR 2015:py OR 2016:py OR 2017:py OR 2018:py OR 2019:py OR 2020:py OR 2021:py OR 2022:py OR 2023:py OR 2024:py OR 2025:py) AND [humans]/lim

PSYCHINFO

exp Cognitive Impairment/ OR (Cognit* Dysfunction* or Cognit* Disorder* or Cognit* Impairment* or Cognit* Decline* or Mental Deterioration* or Cognit* function* or Cognit* outcome* or Cognit* deficit* or Cognit* progression* or Cognit* status or Cognit* characteristic* or Cognit* defect*).ab,ti.

AND

("clinically isolated syndrome" or "demyelinating disorder" or "demyelinating disease" or "optic neuritis" or "multiple sclerosis" or Radiologically isolated Syndrome or RIS).ab,ti. OR exp Multiple Sclerosis/ OR exp Optic Neuritis/

AND

(metasynthesis.md. or "systematic review".md. or "Systematic Review"/ or "systematic reviews as topic".mh. or ("Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews" or evidence report technology assessment or evidence report technology assessment summary).jn. or (((((comprehensive or comprehensively) adj (analysis or review or reviewed)) or ((literature or scoping) adj (search or searches))).ti,ab,id. not "narrative review".ti.) and (database or databases or cinahl or cochrane or embase or psycinfo or pubmed or medline or scopus or (web adj1 science) or ((bibliographic or literature) adj (review or reviews)) or (((electronic adj (database or databases)) or (databases adj3 searched)) and (eligibility or excluded or exclusion or included or inclusion))).ti,ab,id.) or (((comparative adj effectiveness) and (effectiveness adj review)) or ((critical adj interpretive) and ((interpretive adj review) or (interpretive adj synthesis))).ti,ab,id. or ((diagnostic adj test) and ((accuracy adj review) or (accuracy adj reviews) or (accuracy adj studies) or (accuracy adj study)) and (meta-analysis or scoping or systematic)).ti,ab,id. or ((evidence adj assessment) and GRADE).ti,ab,id. or ((evidence adj2 gap) and (gap adj map)).ti,ab,id. or ((evidence adj mapping) or (evidence adj review) or (exploratory adj review) or (framework adj synthesis) or (mapping adj review)).ti,ab,id. or ((meta adj (epidemiological or ethnographic or ethnography or interpretation or narrative or review or study or synthesis or summary or theory)) or metaethnographic or metaethnography or metasynthesis).ti,ab,id. or ((methodological or methodology) adj1 review).ti,ab,id. or ((mixed adj methods) and (methods adj1 (review or synthesis))).ti,ab,id. or ((narrative adj1 synthesis) or (overview adj4 reviews) or ("PRISMA" adj4 (guideline or guidelines or preferred or reporting or requirements)) or (PRISMA adj "P")).ti,ab,id. or (((prognostic or psychometric) adj1 review) or ((qualitative adj (evidence or research)) and ((evidence or research) adj synthesis))).ti,ab,id. or (((rapid adj evidence) and (evidence adj assessment)) or (rapid adj realist) or (rapid adj2 (review or reviews)) or (realist adj2 (review or reviews or syntheses or synthesis))).ti,ab,id. or (((review adj economic) and (economic adj1 (evaluation or evaluations))) or ((scoping or systematic) adj2 (review or reviews or studies or study))).ti,ab,id. or ((review adj1 reviews) or ((systematic adj evidence) and (evidence adj map)) or (systematic adj2 mapping) or (systematic adj2 literature) or (systematic adj2 (Embase or Medline or PsycInfo or PubMed)) or (systematic adj2 (review or reviews)) or ((systematical or systematically) adj2 (review or reviewed reviews)) or (systematically adj identified) or (systematized adj review) or (umbrella adj (review or reviews))).ti,ab,id.)

limit to (english and yr="2001 -Current" and human)

CINAHL

(TI "clinically isolated syndrome" OR AB "clinically isolated syndrome" OR TI "demyelinating disorder" OR AB "demyelinating disorder" OR TI "demyelinating disease" OR AB "demyelinating disease" OR TI "optic neuritis" OR AB "optic neuritis" OR TI "multiple sclerosis" OR AB "multiple sclerosis" OR (MH "Demyelinating Autoimmune Diseases, CNS") OR (MH "Optic Neuritis") OR (MH "Demyelinating Diseases") OR (MH "Multiple Sclerosis")) AND ((MH "Cognition Disorders") OR TI (Cognit* Dysfunction* OR Cognit* Disorder* OR Cognit* Impairment* OR Cognit* Decline* OR Mental Deterioration* OR Cognit* function* OR Cognit* outcome* OR Cognit* deficit* OR Cognit* progression* OR Cognit* status OR Cognit* characteristic* OR Cognit* defect*) OR AB (Cognit* Dysfunction* OR Cognit* Disorder* OR Cognit* Impairment* OR Cognit* Decline* OR Mental Deterioration* OR Cognit* function* OR Cognit* outcome* OR Cognit* deficit* OR Cognit* progression* OR Cognit* status OR Cognit*))

AND

(MH "meta analysis" OR MH "systematic review" OR MH "Technology, Medical/EV" OR PT "systematic review" OR PT "meta analysis" OR (((TI systematic* OR AB systematic*) N3 ((TI review* OR AB review*) OR (TI overview* OR AB overview*))) OR ((TI methodologic* OR AB methodologic*) N3 ((TI review* OR AB review*) OR (TI overview* OR AB overview*))) OR (((TI quantitative OR AB quantitative) N3 ((TI review* OR AB review*) OR (TI overview* OR AB overview*) OR (TI synthes* OR AB synthes*))) OR ((TI research OR AB research) N3 ((TI integrati* OR AB integrati*) OR (TI overview* OR AB overview*))) OR (((TI integrative OR AB integrative) N3 ((TI review* OR AB review*) OR (TI overview* OR AB overview*))) OR ((TI collaborative OR AB collaborative) N3 ((TI review* OR AB review*) OR (TI overview* OR AB overview*))) OR ((TI pool* OR AB pool*) N3 (TI analy* OR AB analy*)) OR ((TI "data synthes*" OR AB "data synthes*") OR (TI "data extraction*" OR AB "data extraction*") OR (TI "data abstraction*" OR AB "data abstraction*")) OR ((TI handsearch* OR AB handsearch*) OR (TI "hand search*" OR AB "hand search*")) OR ((TI "mantel haenszel" OR AB "mantel haenszel") OR (TI peto OR AB peto) OR (TI "der simonian" OR AB "der simonian") OR (TI dersimonian OR AB dersimonian) OR (TI "fixed effect*" OR AB "fixed effect*") OR (TI "latin square*" OR AB "latin square*")) OR ((TI "met analy*" OR AB "met analy*") OR (TI metanaly* OR AB metanaly*) OR (TI "technology assessment*" OR AB "technology assessment*") OR (TI HTA OR AB HTA) OR (TI HTAs OR AB HTAs) OR (TI "technology overview*" OR AB "technology overview*") OR (TI "technology appraisal*" OR AB "technology appraisal*")) OR ((TI "meta regression*" OR AB "meta regression*") OR (TI metaregression* OR AB metaregression*)) OR (TI meta-analy* OR TI metaanaly* OR TI "systematic review*" OR TI "biomedical technology assessment*" OR TI "bio-medical technology assessment*" OR AB meta-analy* OR AB metaanaly* OR AB "systematic review*" OR AB "biomedical technology assessment*" OR AB "bio-medical technology assessment*" OR MW meta-analy* OR MW metaanaly* OR MW "systematic review*" OR MW "biomedical technology assessment*" OR MW "bio-medical technology assessment*") OR ((TI medline OR AB medline OR MW medline) OR (TI cochrane OR AB cochrane OR MW cochrane) OR (TI pubmed OR AB

pubmed OR MW pubmed) OR (TI medlars OR AB medlars OR MW medlars) OR (TI embase OR AB embase OR MW embase) OR (TI cinahl OR AB cinahl OR MW cinahl)) OR (SO Cochrane OR SO health technology assessment OR SO evidence report) OR ((TI comparative OR AB comparative) N3 ((TI efficacy OR AB efficacy) OR (TI effectiveness OR AB effectiveness))) OR ((TI "outcomes research" OR AB "outcomes research") OR (TI "relative effectiveness" OR AB "relative effectiveness")) OR (((TI indirect OR AB indirect) OR (TI "indirect treatment" OR AB "indirect treatment")) OR (TI mixed-treatment OR AB mixed-treatment) OR (TI bayesian OR AB bayesian)) N3 (TI comparison* OR AB comparison*) OR ((TI multi* OR AB multi*) N3 (TI treatment OR AB treatment) N3 (TI comparison* OR AB comparison*)) OR ((TI mixed OR AB mixed) N3 (TI treatment OR AB treatment) N3 ((TI meta-analy* OR AB meta-analy*) OR (TI metaanaly* OR AB metaanaly*))) OR (TI "umbrella review*" OR AB "umbrella review*") OR ((TI multi* OR AB multi*) N2 (TI paramet* OR AB paramet*) N2 (TI evidence OR AB evidence) N2 (TI synthesis OR AB synthesis)) OR ((TI multiparamet* OR AB multiparamet*) N2 (TI evidence OR AB evidence) N2 (TI synthesis OR AB synthesis)) OR ((TI multi-paramet* OR AB multi-paramet*) N2 (TI evidence OR AB evidence) N2 (TI synthesis OR AB synthesis))

Limiters - Publication Date: 20010101-.....

Narrow by Language: - english

COCHRANE LIBRARY

(MeSH descriptor: [Cognitive Dysfunction] explode all trees OR (Cognit* Dysfunction* or Cognit* Disorder* or Cognit* Impairment* or Cognit* Decline* or Mental Deterioration* or Cognit* function* or Cognit* outcome* or Cognit* deficit* or Cognit* progression* or Cognit* status or Cognit* characteristic* or Cognit* defect*):ti,ab,kw)

AND

(MeSH descriptor: [Multiple Sclerosis] explode all trees OR MeSH descriptor: [Optic Neuritis] explode all trees OR "clinically isolated syndrome" or "demyelinating disorder" or "demyelinating disease" or "optic neuritis" or "multiple sclerosis" or Radiologically isolated Syndrome or RIS)

Appendix 2 – Items data extraction sheet

- DOI
- First author name, year
- Design of studies included in the SR
- Type of review (Intervention, diagnostic, prognostic)
- N of studies included in the SR
- N of studies included in the SR assessing CI
- Search date (year) from
- Search date (month/year) to
- N of databases searched
- Overall N of patients included in the SR
- Age (mean)
- Education level reported in the SR
- Proportion of female-identifying participants
- Proportion of male identifying participants
- Number of non-binary participants
- Country of included studies reported in the SR
- Ethnicity of participants reported in the SR
- Employment status reported in the SR
- MS phenotype
- MS diagnostic criteria reported in the SR
- McDonalds diagnostic criteria reported in the SR
- Mean disease duration
- CI definition provided
- Cognitive domains reported in the SR
- Type of CI assessment (individual test/test battery)
- Name of test battery
- Name of individual tests
- EDSS (Motor impairment) reported in the SR
- EDSS range across included studies
- Psychiatric comorbidities reported in the SR
- Fatigue (cognitive or physical) reported in the SR
- JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for systematic reviews and research syntheses